

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 02/11/2015 – 06/11/2015

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Plans:

- Work on PhD proposals and generate paper ideas and we await feedback to version 3
- Mary and Emmanuel to look for topics where students in their respective departments can help
- Emmanuel to explore alternative uplinks based on transmission power, frequency, cost and atmospheric factors affecting radio signals.
- All to begin a systems analysis for the open source version of the RS firmware and assign tasks

Activities:

- Version 3 of the evaluation report was sent out and feedback received. The feedback was discussed and activities leading to an updated version were scheduled.
- Analysis of suitability of alternative uplinks by considering various factors such as transmission power, cost, transmission frequency and equipment, and also their behavior in various atmospheric conditions was started as work in progress by Emmanuel.
- Three topics were proposed to the department of computer studies at DIT by Emmanuel

Plans for next week

- Discussion of firmware architecture of RS mote to be included in the design proposal
- Begin and conclude work on Revision 4 of Evaluation Report
- Continue to work on PhD Proposal documents